

Giant Baker's Cyst open surgery excision: A case report

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Abstract

We report the case of a 55-year-old patient with a giant popliteal cyst associated with grade 2 gonarthrosis, causing pain and discomfort on knee flexion. MRI revealed a voluminous cloistered cystic mass communicating with the joint cavity, unmodified after contrast, measuring 200×80mm, associated with femorotibial and femoropatellar chondropathy.

the patient underwent complete open surgical excision of the cyst with repair of the capsule. After 06 months of follow-up no recurrence of the cyst was observed.

The aim of this article is to present a successful surgical management of a symptomatic giant popliteal cyst.

Keywords: Baker's cyst; Popliteal cyst; Knee; Rheumatoid arthritis; Synovium

1. Introduction

Baker's cyst, or popliteal cyst, is a fluid-filled mass that is a distention of a preexisting bursa in the popliteal fossa, most commonly the gastrocnemio-semimembranosus bursa. This bursa is unique in that it communicates with the knee joint, unlike other periarticular bursae, via an opening in the joint capsule posterior to the medial femoral condyle. Many have theorized that this opening creates a valve-like mechanism in the presence of effusion that contributes to the formation of these cysts in adults.

Popliteal cysts rarely manifest alone and are most often found in conjunction with other intra-articular pathologies and inflammatory conditions, such as osteoarthritis, meniscus tears, and rheumatoid arthritis (1). In this report, we present a giant Baker's cyst in a Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patient expanding to the mid-thigh.

2. Case

A 55-year-old female patient noted a swelling in the popliteal fossa with knee flexion discomfort. Examination revealed a voluminous mass occupying popliteal fossa, soft and painless with no signs of inflammation reaching mid-thigh, we noted a full extension and 120° flexion of the knee.

MRI showed a voluminous cystic mass in T1 hypersignal, T2 hypersignal, unenhanced after intravenous injection of contrast medium, measuring 200mm in height and 80mm in anteroposterior diameter and communicating with the joint cavity. This collection is associated with femorotibial and femoropatellar pinching and meniscal degeneration [Fig1].

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Ultrasound-guided aspiration with corticosteroid injection is a relatively low-risk and successful procedure for the treatment of knee osteoarthritis complicated with a popliteal cyst.

Another option is a similar procedure in which corticosteroid is injected directly into the popliteal cyst.

Acebes et al. reported successful results following aspiration of cyst contents and KS injection in osteoarthritis related cases [3]. In similar cases, Bandinelli et al. also reported successful results using US- guided steroid injection directly into the cyst and intraarticular steroid injection; both methods were considered effective [4]. In the treatment of Baker's cyst accompanied with RA, Hofman-González et al. stated that methotrexate application to the cyst may be an alternative method for patients with surgical risk factors [5].

Although conservative and minimally invasive measures are available to treat some of the conditions associated with popliteal cysts, not all may improve without invasive intervention. Currently, arthroscopic procedures are most commonly used to treat the conditions associated with popliteal cysts and to address cysts directly.

In rare cases, where the cyst remains symptomatic after treatment of the underlying disorder or where no origin has been found, surgical excision may be considered.

When surgical treatment of a popliteal cyst is indicated, three main surgical techniques are available, notably the common posterior approach, the posteromedial approach according to Hughston, and the medial intra-articular approach.

The popliteal cyst usually lies between the medial head of the gastrocnemius muscle and the semimembranosus tendon. The posterior as well as the posteromedial approach are suitable for removing the cyst. With a medial intra-articular approach only the communication of the cyst with the joint can be closed without removal of the cyst [6].

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study

Authors' contributions

All authors contributed to the patient's care and to the drafting of the manuscript. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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